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Robust Recoverable Matching Problems

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Abstract

In this thesis, we define and study the robust recoverable matching problem which is motivated by real-life applications, for both stable matchings and perfect matchings. On the algorithmic side, we design an efficient LP-based algorithm for the Checking version of the robust recoverable matching problem, in the settings of both stable matching and perfect matching. Towards the goal of solving the Finding version of the robust recoverable matching problem, we study the LP formulations of the problem for perfect matching by computing a lower bound of its integrality gap, whereas for the problem for stable matching, we prove a property of one-side optimal stable matching which gives a hint that the Finding problem for stable matching can be efficiently solved. On the complexity side, we establish hardness results for the Finding version of the robust recoverable perfect matching problem, with respect to different values of parameters. Moreover, we prove a structural result of stable matchings that rotation is a special pivoting but not the other way around, which relates the lattice structure of stable matchings with its polytope structure.

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1 Introduction

1.1 Problems and Definitions

The motivation of this paper is the following real-world stable matching¹ problem from the math section of l'École polytechnique fédérale de Lausanne (EPFL).

Suppose that there is a group of students and a group of semester projects, where the number of projects is larger than (or equal to) the number of students. We want to match them based on their mutual preferences over the opposite group. After we have found a stable matching of this instance using whatever techniques, some projects become unavailable, that is, they are deleted from the matching instance. The problem is that we want to recover this stable matching by re-matching the minimum number of students.

To rigorously formulate this problem, we introduce the following definitions which will be used throughout the paper. The matching instance defined below is the key input of our algorithmic problems.

Definition 1.1. A matching instance $\mathcal{F} = (G, P)$ contains

- a bipartite graph $G = (A \cup B, E)$ where $|A| = n$, $|B| = m$, $n \leq m$, and
- a property P of matching, such as stable, perfect, A -perfect, maximum-cardinality, etc.

Note that if the property P is (the matching being) stable, then the matching instance contains also preference lists of elements of A and B for the opposite group, and the bipartite graph is assumed to be complete.

Remark. In this paper, we focus on the matching instance where P is (the matching being) **stable** and **A -perfect**. We assume this unless specified otherwise. Sometimes we refer the elements of A as students and elements of B as projects, which is consistent with the background.

Example. Consider the following matching instances shown in Figure 1, where the left one is a stable matching instance with a complete bipartite graph of 2 students and 3 projects, and the right one is a A -perfect matching instance with a bipartite graph of 3 students and 5 projects. In the left instance, the numbers written on the edges represent the preference lists of both students and projects. For example A1 prefers B1 to B2 to B3, and B2 prefers A2 to A1.

Definition 1.2 (Robust recoverable). Given a matching instance $\mathcal{F} = (G = (A \cup B, E), P)$ and two integers $r, s \in \mathbb{N}$, a matching M is called *r -robust s -recoverable* with respect to the property P , if M has property P for any deletion $R \subseteq B$ of size r with $r \leq m - n$, there exists an matching M' of the new instance $\mathcal{F}' = (G' = (A \cup B', E), P)$ after deleting R , such that M' has property P and $d(M, M') \leq r + s$, where d is the distance between two matchings defined as

$$d(M, M') := |\{a \in A : M(a) \neq M'(a)\}|.$$

¹The notion of stable matching is defined in Section 2. So far we don't really need its definition to state the problem.

Figure 1: Examples of the matching instance

Remark. Here the parameter r is the degree of robustness which is the number of deletion of projects (nodes in B), and s is the degree of recoverability, which is the number of **extra** rematches allowed to recover the property P .

Note that we use the extra number of rematches to measure recoverability, since for matching M and property P being stable or A -perfect, when deleting $R \subseteq M(A)$, $|R| = r$ we need to rematch at least r students which are the elements in A that are matched to R in M .

For robustness, we can also consider only the deletion of nodes from the matching, i.e., the deletion subset $R \subseteq M(A) \subseteq B$ of size r . This leads to a similar definition.

Definition 1.3 (Weakly robust recoverable). Given a matching instance $\mathcal{F} = (G = (A \cup B, E), P)$, a matching M is called *weakly r -robust s -recoverable* with respect to the property P , if M has property P for any deletion $R \subseteq M(A)$ of size r with $r \leq m - n$, there exists an matching M' of the new instance $\mathcal{F}' = (G' = (A \cup B', E), P)$ after deleting R , such that M' has property P and $d(M, M') \leq r + s$.

Remark. If matching M is r -robust s -recoverable of a given instance \mathcal{F} , then M is also weakly r -robust s -recoverable of instance \mathcal{F} .

Example. To illustrate this definition, let us consider the following matching instance where the bipartite graph is of size $|A| = 3$, $|B| = 5$ and the property to be recovered is A -perfect. Take an A -perfect matching $M = \{A1 - B2, A2 - B1, A3 - B5\}$. See Figure 2 for an illustration. The matching M is 1-robust 1-recoverable, hence also weakly 1-robust 1-recoverable. This is because

- Deletion of B1 requires rematching A2 to B3: 0 extra rematch;
- Deletion of B2 requires rematching A1 to B4: 0 extra rematch;
- Deletion of B3 or B4 requires no rematch.
- Deletion of B5 requires rematching A3 to B2 and rematching A1 to B4 : 1 extra rematch.

Figure 2: A perfect matching instance with one of its matchings M colored in red

See Figure 3 for an illustration. The matching M is not weakly 2-robust s -recoverable for any $s \in \mathbb{N}$, hence not 2-robust s -recoverable for any $s \in \mathbb{N}$. This is because after we delete $B2$ and $B5$ there is no perfect matching. See Figure 4 for an illustration. We denote this case as (weakly) 2-robust ∞ -recoverable.

Example. The following example shows that weakly robust recoverable can be strictly weaker than robust recoverable. Consider an instance with 3 students and 5 projects with a different A -perfect matching $N = \{A1 - B1, A2 - B2, A3 - B4\}$ colored in red, as shown in Figure 5.

Consider the case $r = 2$, then N is weakly 2-robust 0-recoverable, but 2-robust ∞ -recoverable since after deletion of $B4$ and $B5$ the new instance has no A -perfect matching.

Main Questions

There are two types of questions which we address in this paper.

1. **Algorithmic and complexity questions** of (weakly) robust recoverable matching problem:

Given a matching instance $\mathcal{F} = (G, P)$ where $G = (A \cup B, E)$, $|A| \leq |B|$ and two integers $r, s \in \mathbb{N}$,

Figure 3: Illustrations of M being 1-robust 1-recoverable

Figure 4: Illustrations of M being 2-robust ∞ -recoverable

we formulate the following two problems parameterized by r and s , which are formally defined in Section 3 and Section 4 respectively.

- **CHECKING** problem: for a given matching M satisfies property P , check if M is (weakly) r -robust s -recoverable.
- **FINDING** problem: find (or decide if there exists) a matching M which satisfies property P and is (weakly) r -robust s -recoverable.

These two decision problems also have **optimization** versions: given a matching instance $\mathcal{F} = (G, P)$ where $G = (A \cup B, E)$, $|A| \leq |B|$ and an integer $r \in \mathbb{N}$,

- **CHECKING-OPT** problem: for a given matching M satisfies property P , find the minimum s such that M is (weakly) r -robust s -recoverable.
- **FINDING-OPT** problem: find the minimum s such that there exists a matching M which satisfies property P and is (weakly) r -robust s -recoverable.

Note that one can also study the optimization problem of given s maximizing r for both CHECKING and FINDING. We will only focus on the problem of given r minimizing s .

Figure 5: Example where weakly robust recoverable is strictly weaker than robust recoverable

In this paper, we mainly study the CHECKING and FINDING problems for both stable matching and perfect matching.

2. Structural question of stable matchings:

The set of stable matchings is equipped with both the **lattice** structure and the **polytope** structure as show in Section 2. To traverse the lattice of stable matching, we have the notion of **rotation** $M \rightarrow M/\rho$; to traverse the polytope of stable matching, we have the notion of **pivoting** which transforms a stable matching to an adjacent stable matching.

The question is, how are these two notions related to each other? Are they equivalent?

1.2 Our Contributions

Our main results is the following, corresponding to the main questions mentioned above.

1. For the algorithm and complexity question,
 - We design a polynomial-time algorithm for the CHECKING problem with constant r for stable matching. Our approach is LP-based, by using the integral polytope structure of stable matchings. See Section 3.1 for details.
 - We prove some hardness results of the FINDING problem for perfect matching, with different values of r and s . See Section 4.1 for details.
2. For the structural question, we prove that rotation is a special pivoting and give examples which shows that the converse is not true. As a byproduct, the examples also imply that the edges of stable matching polytope is not a subset of the edges of matching polytope. See Section 5 for details.
3. We also find the following results which brings insights to our algorithm and complexity question of robust recoverable matching problem.

At the end of Section 3.1, we discuss the difficulty of extending the LP-based algorithm to higher order r . In Section 3.2, we provides formulations for solving FINDING problem for stable matching. We attack the FINDING problem from another point of view, by considering a special stable matching called the B -optimal stable matching, in Section 3.3. We prove a property of the B -optimal stable matching in the setting of robust recoverable problem, which suggests that it is potentially “more recoverable” than others.

In Section 4.2 we compute a lower bound of the integrality gap of the FINDING problem for perfect matching. We propose a conjecture to get a better algorithm of the CHECKING problem for perfect matching in Section 4.3.

1.3 Related Work

We first review work related to the robustness of stable matching.

The closest work related to ours is the robustness problem studied in [7][8][9], where the key notion is called supermatch. The definition of which is very similar to our Definition 1.2, except that for the

notion of robustness, instead of removing vertices, they do not allow certain edges to show up in the stable matching.² They design a polynomial-time algorithm for checking problem with $r = 1$ and establish the NP-hardness result for finding problem with $r = 1$ and $s = 1$, both in their setting of robustness. A summary of their results can be found in [10].

There are other concepts of robustness of stable matching. In [5], they study the following question of finding a matching which is stable under two “nearby” instances, where “nearby” means that two instances differ by only one agents’ preference list. They introduce a probabilistic model for their question. Their follow-up work [6] extends the results to general cases, where more agents are allowed to do swaps in their preference lists. Another concept is defined in [1], where they study the question of finding a matching which is stable under certain number of swaps in any agents’ preference lists. However, all literature mentioned above define the robustness of stable matchings with respect to swapping elements in the preference lists, which is quite different from our definition of robust recoverable. Also they only study the robustness but not recoverability.

Let us review work related to the robustness of perfect matching. In [3], they define the notion of (weakly) robust recoverable where robustness is about deleting edges. Their notion of robust recoverable is also parameterized by two parameters r and s , which has similar meaning to ours. They prove several structural results about (weakly) robust recoverable and establish the NP-completeness of the FINDING problem when $r = 1$ and $s = 2k$ for $k \geq 2$.

A closely related problem is the matching interdiction problem, which has been mostly studied in the setting of perfect matching. This problem asks for the minimum number of deletion of either vertices or nodes, such that the graph no longer has certain property (for example, the graph no longer has perfect matching), which is called the interdiction (or preclusion) number. The weighted interdiction problems of deleting edges³ and deleting vertices are studied in [23], where some hardness results are proved for interdiction problem with extra conditions added. In [3], they prove that the problem of computing the (unweighted) interdiction number⁴ for any bipartite graph is NP-complete. On the other hand, the matching interdiction problem of deleting vertices is polynomial-time solvable by using linear programming, as shown in [15].

Some other related work include [13] which studies different types of robust recoverable problems in the setting of not only bipartite matching but also matroids basis and stable set, and [11] which studies the robustness of online b-matching.

²These edges can still be blocking edges, which is why we use the word “disallowing” edges rather than deleting edges.

³Some people call it the matching preclusion problem.

⁴It is also called the preclusion number.

2 Preliminaries

In this section we briefly go through the basic knowledge of stable matching and the lattice and polytope structure of stable matchings. This section is not intended to be exhaustive; it primarily defines concepts that will be referenced later in the paper. For an overview of stable matchings, we refer to [12]. Throughout this section, we use the matching instance as in Definition 1.1.

Stable Matching

The following notion is originally defined in [2]. Check [14] for details.

Definition 2.1 (Stable matching). An edge ab (also denoted as (a, b)) is a *blocking edge* of matching M , if $ab \notin M$, a prefers b to $M(a)$, and b prefers a to $M(b)$. Here $M(a)$ is the partner of a in M , similar for $M(b)$. A matching M is *stable* if there is no blocking edge with respect to M . An edge is *stable* if it appears in a stable matching. An edge is *fixed* if it appears in every stable matching.

There are two classical results of stable matching.

Theorem 2.2 (Gale-Shapley, 1962). Stable matching always exists and can be computed in polynomial-time.

Theorem 2.3 (Gale-Sotomayor, 1985). The set of matched vertices are identical in all stable matchings.

Remark. The number of stable matchings can be exponential.

Stable Matching Lattice

We now introduce the lattice structure of stable matchings. A general reference can be found in [14].

Definition 2.4 (Preference). A student $a \in A$ *weakly prefers* M to M' , denoted as $M \succeq_a M'$, if either a prefers $M(a)$ to $M'(a)$ or $M(a) = M'(a)$. Similarly we define the weakly preference for project $b \in B$.

There are two special stable matchings.

Definition 2.5 (Optimal stable matchings). A stable matching M_0 is called *A-optimal*, if for any student $a \in A$ and for any stable matching M , a weakly prefers M_0 to M . A stable matching M_z is called *B-optimal*, if for any project $b \in B$ and for any stable matching M , b weakly prefers M_z to M .

Both *A-optimal* and *B-optimal* stable matchings are unique. We denote them as M_0 and M_z respectively. This definition will show up again in Section 3.3, when we discuss the FINDING problem for stable matching.

We now define the lattice structure of stable matchings step by step as follows:

$$\text{Set of stable matchings} \xrightarrow{\text{partial order } \succeq} \text{Poset} \xrightarrow{\text{join}\uparrow \text{ \& meet}\downarrow} \text{Lattice} \longrightarrow \text{Distributive Lattice}.$$

Definition 2.6 (Partial order). Define a partial order \succeq on the set of all stable matchings, where for any stable matchings M and M' , we have $M \succeq M'$ if and only if all students weakly prefer M to M' .

Definition 2.7. For two stable matchings M, M' , define

$$M \vee M' = M^\uparrow,$$

where M^\uparrow is the set of student-project pairs, in which each student is matched to their more preferred project between M and M' . Similarly, define

$$M \wedge M' = M^\downarrow,$$

where M^\downarrow is the set of student-project pairs, in which each student is matched to their less preferred student between M and M' .

Proposition 2.8. As defined above, M^\uparrow is the *join* of M and M' , i.e.,

- $M^\uparrow \geq M$ and $M^\uparrow \geq M'$,
- for any M'' such that $M'' \geq M$ and $M'' \geq M'$, $M'' \geq M^\uparrow$

Similarly, M^\downarrow is the *meet* of M and M' , i.e.,

- $M \geq M^\downarrow$ and $M' \geq M^\downarrow$,
- for any M'' such that $M \geq M''$ and $M' \geq M''$, $M^\downarrow \geq M''$.

Theorem 2.9. The set of stable matchings, equipped with the partial order \geq , the join \vee and meet \wedge operators defined above, forms a lattice which is *distributive*.

The notion of rotation provides insights of the structure of stable matching lattice. The definition is mostly taken from Definition 3.4 of [1].

Definition 2.10 (Successor, rotation). Let M be a stable matching. A *successor* of the agent $a \in A$, denoted as $\text{succ}_M(a)$ is the first project $b \in B$ on the preference list of a such that b is matched under M and prefers a to its partner $M(b)$. The preference lists of a and $\text{succ}_M(a)$ are illustrated as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} a &: \cdots M(a) \cdots \text{succ}_M(a) \cdots \\ \text{succ}_M(a) &: \cdots a \cdots M(\text{succ}_M(a)) \cdots \end{aligned}$$

A *rotation* is a sequence of pairs in $A \times B$:

$$\rho = ((a_0, b_0), (a_1, b_1), \dots, (a_{\ell-1}, b_{\ell-1}))$$

such that there exists a stable matching M where for each $i \in \{0, 1, \dots, \ell - 1\}$ we have $M(a_i) = b_i$ and $\text{succ}_M(a_i) = b_{i+1}$ ⁵ The rotation is said to be *exposed* in M . From M , by replacing each pair (a_i, b_i) with (a_i, b_{i+1}) (cyclic rematch), we get another stable⁶ matching denoted as M/ρ .

We will refer to this definition again in Section 5.

⁵The index is taken modulo ℓ .

⁶It is not hard to check that this matching is indeed stable.

Remark. We end this part by giving some remarks about rotation, similar to the ones given in Section 2.3 of [16].

- After each rotation, the project matched to each student become “weakly worse” and the student matched to each project become “weakly better”.
- In the stable matching lattice, by applying an appropriate sequence of rotations, one can traverse the lattice from the A -optimal stable matching M_0 to the B -optimal stable matching M_z .

An example of stable matching lattice can be found at this [example](#) in Section 5.

Stable Matching Polytope

Solving robustness problem related to stable matchings relies crucially on the polytope structure of stable matchings. We first review the matching polytope. For this part check [18] for reference.

Definition 2.11 (Incidence vector). The *incidence vector* of a matching M is a vector $x(M)^7 \in \{0, 1\}^E$, such that

$$x_e = \begin{cases} 1, & \text{if } e \in M \\ 0, & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases}$$

We often identify a matching with its incidence vector. The next theorem gives a characterization of matching.

Theorem 2.12. A vector $x \in \mathbb{R}^{A \times B} \cong \mathbb{R}^E$ is a matching if and only if it is an integer solution of the following system of linear inequalities:

$$\sum_{b \in B} x_{a,b} \leq 1, \quad \text{for each } a \in A, \quad (1)$$

$$\sum_{a \in A} x_{a,b} \leq 1, \quad \text{for each } b \in B, \quad (2)$$

$$x_{a,b} \geq 0, \quad \text{for each } a \in A, b \in B. \quad (3)$$

Definition 2.13 (Matching polytope). The *matching polytope* is defined as the feasible solutions of linear inequalities (1), (2), and (3). Denote it as P_M . The element of P_M is called the *fractional matching*.

Theorem 2.14 (Birkhoff). Each fractional matching is a convex combination of matchings. Equivalently, the matching polytope P_M is integral.

A stable matching can be characterized by adding one type of constraint to the characterization of matching as in Theorem 2.12.

Theorem 2.15. A vector $x \in \mathbb{R}^{A \times B}$ is a stable matching if and only if it is an integer solution of the linear inequalities (1), (2), (3), together with

$$x_{a,b} + \sum_{b' >_a b} x_{a,b'} + \sum_{a' >_b a} x_{a',b} \geq 1, \quad \text{for each } a \in A, b \in B. \quad (4)$$

We call this type of inequality the *stability constraint*.

⁷For simplicity, we sometimes only write x .

Definition 2.16 (Stable matching polytope). The *stable matching polytope* is defined as the feasible solutions of linear inequalities (1), (2), (3), and (4). Denote it as P_{SM} . The element of P_{SM} is called the *fractional stable matching*.

Theorem 2.17 (Vande Vate, 1989). Each fractional stable matching is a convex combination of stable matchings. Equivalently, the stable matching polytope P_{SM} is integral.

Remark. This result is first formulated and proved in [22], later simplified and slightly extended in [19]. A geometric proof of the integrality of stable matching polytope is given in [21]. Their proof is constructive and suggests a way to round a fractional stable matching to (integral) stable matching. However their proof only works for balanced complete stable matching. Another simple proof of the integrality can be found in [20].

We will use the integrality of P_{SM} (Theorem 2.17) extensively when solving the CHECKING problem, which will be discussed in Section 3.1.

3 Robust Recoverable Stable Matching

In this section, we study the robust recoverable problems for stable matching. First in Section 3.1, we provide a LP-based polynomial-time algorithm for the CHECKING problem of stable matching when r is a constant. At the end of Section 3.1, we discuss the limit of our approach and possibility of extending our algorithm to higher order r . Next we turns to the FINDING problem of stable matching in Section 3.2 and gives several formulations of this problem. Finally we consider in Section 3.3 a special stable matching, called the B -optimal stable matching as defined in Definition 2.5. We prove one of its properties which gives us hope of obtaining a fast algorithm for FINDING problem.

Note that we specifically focus on robust recoverable matching since the algorithm and formulations apply also to weakly robust recoverable matching.

The two main problems of this section are the following, which is based on the definition of matching instance and robust recoverable applying to stable matching. Check Definition 1.1 and 1.2 for details.

Problem 1 CHECKING r -ROBUST s -RECOVERABLE STABLE MATCHING (CHECKING- (r, s) -SM)

Input: A stable matching instance \mathcal{J} , a stable matching M , two integers $r, s \in \mathbb{N}$.

Question: Is M a r -robust s -recoverable stable matching of \mathcal{J} ?

Problem 2 FINDING r -ROBUST s -RECOVERABLE STABLE MATCHING (FINDING- (r, s) -SM)

Input: A stable matching instance \mathcal{J} , two integers $r, s \in \mathbb{N}$.

Question: Is there a r -robust s -recoverable stable matching of \mathcal{J} ?

As mentioned before, we consider also the optimization version of these two problems:

Problem 3 CHECKING ROBUST RECOVERABLE STABLE MATCHING - OPTIMIZATION (CHECKING-SM-OPT)

Input: A stable matching instance \mathcal{J} , a stable matching M , an integer $r \in \mathbb{N}$.

Question: Find the minimum $s \in \mathbb{N}$ such that M a r -robust s -recoverable stable matching of \mathcal{J} ?

Problem 4 FINDING ROBUST RECOVERABLE STABLE MATCHING - OPTIMIZATION (FINDING-SM-OPT)

Input: A stable matching instance \mathcal{J} , an integer $r \in \mathbb{N}$.

Question: Find the minimum $s \in \mathbb{N}$ such that there is a r -robust s -recoverable stable matching of \mathcal{J} ?

The following example shows that for some stable matching, even deleting just one node may cause complete re-matching for recovery, which breaks the hope of getting an universal upper bound for s .

Example (Complete re-matching for recovery). Our original example is a “zigzag” bipartite graph between 3 students and 4 projects as shown in Figure 6. For stable matching $\{A1 - B1, A2 - B2, A3 - B3\}$ colored in red, deletion of $B1$ will cause a complete re-matching to get the new stable matching $\{A1 - B2, A2 - B3, A3 - B4\}$ colored in blue.

Figure 6: An example of deleting 1 node which causes a complete re-matching for recovery.

We can extend this example to a stable matching instance of n students and $n + 1$ projects, by defining the preferences as follows:

- For each student A_i , $i = 1, \dots, n$, the first choice is B_i , the second choice is B_{i+1} ;
- For each project B_j ,
 - if $j = 2, \dots, n$, the first choice is A_{j-1} , the second choice is A_j ;
 - if $j = 1$ and $j = n + 1$, B_j has only one partner, which is its first choice.

We can extend further to get a stable matching instance where the bipartite graph between n students and $n + 1$ projects is **complete**, by connecting all the unconnected pairs with low preferences for each other. See Figure 7 for an illustration.

3.1 LP-Based Algorithm for CHECKING

The CHECKING problem has been studied in [7] for robust recoverable matching with respect to disallowing certain edges (instead of deleting vertices as in our case), which is mentioned in Section 1.3. They find a polynomial-time algorithm for $r = 1$ and any $s \in \mathbb{N}$, using extensively the notion of rotation of stable matching. In this section, we propose a LP approach which solves the CHECKING problem in polynomial-time for both our problem where robustness is about deleting vertices, and the problem studied in [7] where robustness is about disallowing edges. Moreover our approach applies to any constant r .

Theorem 3.1. CHECKING- (r, s) -SM is polynomial-time solvable, for r being constant and any $s \in \mathbb{N}$.

Figure 7: Completion of example shown in Figure 6

Proof. We start by solving the optimization version of CHECKING first, which is CHECKING-SM-OPT. For any $R \subseteq B$ with $|R| = r$, consider the following integer linear program

$$\begin{aligned}
 \max \quad & \sum_{e \in M} x_e \\
 \text{s.t.} \quad & x \in P_{\text{SM}}(R), \\
 & x \in \{0, 1\}^{E(R)}.
 \end{aligned} \tag{5}$$

where $E(R)$ and $P_{\text{SM}}(R)$ are the set of edges and the stable matching polytope after deletion of R . The objective function is the number of common edges between M and a stable matching x after deleting R . Solve this integer linear program for each $R \subseteq B$ with $|R| = r$. There are $\binom{m}{r}$ many such integer linear programs. Since the stable matching polytope $P_{\text{SM}}(R)$ is integral, solving it takes polynomial-time. Denote the solution as $f(R)$. The solution to CHECKING-SM-OPT is then $\min_{R \subseteq B, |R|=r} f(R)$. The answer to CHECKING- (r, s) -SM is yes, if and only if

$$\min_{R \subseteq B, |R|=r} f(R) \geq n - (r + s).$$

□

Remark. This proof is applicable to the problem of CHECKING robust recoverable for disallowing edges, by simply replacing the polytope of deleting vertices $P_{\text{SM}}(R)$ to the polytope of disallowing edges, which is also integral.

Towards CHECKING Problem with Higher Order r

As mentioned before, the limit of our LP approach shown in Theorem 3.1 is that it gives a polynomial-time algorithm only when r is constant. We wonder if there is a LP-based algorithm for r which is of higher order than constant, for example, for $r = O(\log(n))$ or $O(\sqrt{n})$.

Recall that our LP approach solves the CHECKING problem for every specific deletions and takes the minimum value among them. Instead of using $\binom{m}{r}$ many integer linear programs, we wonder if we can encode all the deletions into one integer linear program of polynomial-size.

Remark. CHECKING- (r, s) -SM is in co-NP, since a no-certificate of CHECKING- (r, s) -SM is a specific deletion R , which can be checked by solving (5).

Suppose that there is a polynomial-size IP-formulation of CHECKING- (r, s) -SM for r (of higher order than constant), then the problem is also in NP. Together with the remark, it will imply that CHECKING- (r, s) -SM is in $\text{NP} \cap \text{co-NP}$, which gives hint that CHECKING- (r, s) -SM is polynomial-time solvable for this r .

3.2 Formulations of FINDING

Now we consider the FINDING problems, namely FINDING- (r, s) -SM and FINDING-SM-OPT. The naive method of finding a robust stable matching by checking all stable matchings fails to be polynomial-time, since there could be exponentially many stable matchings. To attack the FINDING problems, we will discuss various formulations.

Robust recoverable with respect to a specific deletion

We start by considering a problem which is easier than FINDING- (r, s) -SM. Instead of asking for a stable matching which is recoverable with respect to **all** deletions of size r , we ask for a stable matching which is recoverable with respect to a specific deletion R of certain size r . Therefore we have two problems similar to the problems 1 and 2.

Problem 5 CHECKING R -ROBUST s -RECOVERABLE STABLE MATCHING (CHECKING- (R, s) -SM)

Input: A stable matching instance \mathcal{F} , a stable matching M , two integers $r, s \in \mathbb{N}$, a specific deletion subset $R \subseteq B$ with $|R| = r$.

Question: Is M a R -robust s -recoverable stable matching of \mathcal{F} ?

Using the same method as in Section 3.1, this problem CHECKING- (R, s) -SM can be solved in polynomial-time.

Problem 6 FINDING R -ROBUST s -RECOVERABLE STABLE MATCHING (FINDING- (R, s) -SM)

Input: A stable matching instance \mathcal{F} , two integers $r, s \in \mathbb{N}$, a specific deletion subset $R \subseteq B$ with $|R| = r$.

Question: Is there a R -robust s -recoverable stable matching of \mathcal{F} ?

The problem FINDING- (R, s) -SM⁸ can be formulated as a convex program:

$$\begin{aligned}
 \min \quad & \|\text{proj}_R(x) - y\|_1 \\
 \text{s.t.} \quad & x \in P_{\text{SM}}, x \in \{0, 1\}^E, \\
 & y \in P_{\text{SM}}(R), y \in \{0, 1\}^{E(R)},
 \end{aligned} \tag{6}$$

⁸More precisely, here we refer to its optimization version.

where $\text{proj}_R : \mathbb{R}^E \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^{E(R)}$ is the natural projection map. Basically this problem is asking for a vertex x of the original stable matching polytope P_{SM} and a vertex y of the stable matching polytope $P_{\text{SM}}(R)$ after deletion of R , such that the ℓ_1 distance between x and y is minimized. See Figure 8 for an illustration.

Figure 8: Illustration of the formulation (6) of the optimization version of FINDING- (R, s) -SM

Remark. Note that $P_{\text{SM}}(R) \cap P_{\text{SM}} = \emptyset$ unless all elements of R are unmatched in the original instance of P_{SM} . Also to get $P_{\text{SM}}(R)$ from P_{SM} , it does not work if one just lets the component x_e to be zero where the edges e is involved in the deletion R , i.e.,

$$P_{\text{SM}}(R) \neq P_{\text{SM}} \cap \{x \in \mathbb{R}^E : x_e = 0, \forall e \in \delta(v), \forall v \in R\}.$$

We also have to delete the corresponding stability constraints of R .

This formulation can be written as an integer (linear) program as follows.

$$\begin{aligned} \min \quad & \mathbf{1}^T z \\ \text{s.t.} \quad & x \in P_{\text{SM}}, x \in \{0, 1\}^E, \\ & y \in P_{\text{SM}}(R), y \in \{0, 1\}^{E(R)}, \\ & z_i \geq \text{proj}_R(x)_i - y_i, \forall i = 1, 2, \dots, |E(R)|, \\ & z_i \geq y_i - \text{proj}_R(x)_i, \forall i = 1, 2, \dots, |E(R)|. \end{aligned} \tag{7}$$

Now we come back to the FINDING- (r, s) -SM problem which has a similar formulation as (6):

$$\begin{aligned} \min \quad & d \\ \text{s.t.} \quad & x \in P_{\text{SM}}, x \in \{0, 1\}^E, \\ & y_R \in P_{\text{SM}}(R), y_R \in \{0, 1\}^{E(R)}, \forall R \subseteq B, |R| = r, \\ & d \geq \|\text{proj}_R(x) - y_R\|_1, \forall R \subseteq B, |R| = r. \end{aligned} \tag{8}$$

Intuitively, we search for a stable matching x , i.e., a vertex of P_{SM} , with the minimum “radius” d such that the ℓ_1 -ball of radius d centered at x has non-empty intersection with the set of vertices of $P_{\text{SM}}(R)$ for all $R \subseteq B, |R| = r$. This formulation is illustrated below in Figure 9.

Figure 9: Illustration of the formulation (8)

Table 1 lists all the results of robust recoverable stable matching problems we have found so far.

	R -robust (one specific deletion R)	r -robust (all deletions of size r)
CHECKING s -recoverable	Solved	Solved, but not FPT w.r.t. r
FINDING s -recoverable	Open	Open, expected to be W[1]-hard w.r.t. r

Table 1: Results of robust recoverable problems for stable matching

Remark. The most generalized version of FINDING problem for stable matching is the following.

Problem 7 FINDING \mathcal{R} -ROBUST s -RECOVERABLE STABLE MATCHING

Input: A stable matching instance \mathcal{F} , two integers $r, s \in \mathbb{N}$, a collection of deletion subsets \mathcal{R} of polynomial size whose elements $R \in \mathcal{R}$ are $R \subseteq B$ with $|R| = r$.

Question: Is there a \mathcal{R} -robust s -recoverable stable matching of \mathcal{F} ?

This problem can be formulated as follows, similar to (8).

$$\begin{aligned}
 \min \quad & d \\
 \text{s.t.} \quad & x \in P_{\text{SM}}, \quad x \in \{0, 1\}^E, \\
 & y_R \in P_{\text{SM}}(R), \quad y_R \in \{0, 1\}^{E(R)}, \quad \forall R \in \mathcal{R}, \\
 & d \geq \|\text{proj}_R(x) - y_R\|_1, \quad \forall R \in \mathcal{R}.
 \end{aligned} \tag{9}$$

3.3 B -Optimal Stable Matching

We consider the problem from another perspective, which is by thinking the robust recoverability of some special stable matchings. A candidate is the B -optimal stable matching denoted by M_z , given

by Definition 2.5. Our guess is that for any removal of size r , the stable matching which requires the minimum number of rematch/recourse is the B -optimal stable matching M_z . Intuitively this makes sense because in M_z every matched projects is matched to their most preferred student among all the stable matchings, thus after deletion they are less willing to change.

We prove the following property of M_z which gives a hint that our guess might be correct.

Proposition 3.2. For any deletion $R \subseteq B$ and any stable matching M , after deleting R , the number of blocking edges of M_z is less than or equal to the number of blocking edges of M .

Proof. Without loss of generality, consider the case where R is all matched in M_z , i.e., $R \subseteq M_z(A)$. Decompose the set of nodes into different subsets which is illustrated in Figure 10:

$$A = A_1 \cup A_2, \quad B = B_1 \cup B_2 \cup B_3$$

where each subsets are defined as follows:

$$A_1 = M_z(R), \quad A_2 = A \setminus M_z(R) \quad \text{and} \quad B_1 = R, \quad B_2 = M_z(A) \setminus R, \quad B_3 = B \setminus M_z(A).$$

Figure 10: Illustration of the proof of Proposition 3.2. For the stable matching instance, the dotted lines represent the edges of the complete bipartite graph, and the preference lists are omitted in this figure. The B -optimal stable matching M_z is colored in red. The deletion subset R is indicated by the crossmarks.

Claim. For any stable matching M of the original instance and $a \in A, b \in B_2 \cup B_3$, if ab is a blocking edge of M_z after deletion, then $ab \notin M$.

proof of Claim. Suppose not, then

$$a = M(b) \succeq_b M_z(b), \quad ab \notin M_z \implies M(b) \succ_b M_z(b)$$

which contradicts the B -optimality of M_z . □

Consider the following cases of ab .

- $b \in B_2$,

- $a \in A_1$, if ab is a blocking edge of M_z after deletion, then by Claim $ab \notin M$ and

$$a \succ_b M_z(b) \succeq_b M(b), \quad b \succ_a \emptyset$$

which implies that ab is a blocking edge of M after deletion as well.

- $a \in A_2$, then ab is not a blocking edge of M_z after deletion, since for $ab \notin M_z$ before deletion ab is not a blocking edge of M_z , which implies

$$M_z(b) \succ_b a \quad \text{or} \quad M_z(a) \succ_a b.$$

Deletion of B_1 will not affect the validity of those two inequalities.

- $b \in B_3$,

for both M_z and M , there are $|B_3| \cdot |A_1| = (m - n)r$ blocking edges. □

This proposition motivates the following conjecture.

Conjecture 1. For any deletion $R \subseteq B$, the B -optimal stable matching M_z needs the minimum number of extra rematches s .

If Conjecture 1 is true, then the FINDING problem is reduced to CHECKING problem for M_z . Equivalently, checking if M_z is r -robust s -recoverable for any r, s , is at least as hard as finding a r -robust s -recoverable stable matching. The next step is either to prove this conjecture or find a counterexample, i.e., a stable matching instance where M_z need more rematches than some other stable matching, after certain deletion of $R \subseteq B$.

4 Robust Recoverable Perfect Matching

In this section, we study the robust recoverable problems in the setting of perfect bipartite matching. In Section 4.1 we prove three hardness results of the FINDING problem of perfect matching, by proving the hardness result for FINDING problem with $r = 1, s = 0$ and extending it to two general cases: FINDING problem with $1 \leq r \leq \log(n), s = 0$ and FINDING problem with $r = 1, 1 \leq s \leq n$. In Section 4.2 we consider the integrality gap of our formulation of the FINDING problem and provide a lower bound of the integrality gap. We turn to the CHECKING problem in Section 4.3 and make a conjecture for obtaining a better algorithm for CHECKING problem in the setting of perfect matching.

Without loss of generality, we assume that the matching instance always has an A -perfect matching. We will use perfect matching to refer the A -perfect matching in the following discussion.

Remark. The following observations hold for robust recoverable perfect matching:

- If a perfect matching is $(r + 1)$ -robust s -recoverable, then it is r -robust s -recoverable.
- If a perfect matching is r -robust s -recoverable, then it is r -robust $(s + 1)$ -recoverable.
- For any $s \in \mathbb{N}_{\geq 0}$, if a perfect matching is weakly 1-robust s -recoverable, then it is also 1-robust s -recoverable. Therefore when $r = 1$, robust recoverable equivalent to weakly robust recoverable. When $r > 1$, these two notions are not equivalent as illustrated already in [this example](#).

We study the following two problems of perfect matching.

Problem 8 CHECKING r -ROBUST s -RECOVERABLE PERFECT MATCHING (CHECKING- (r, s) -PM)

Input: A perfect matching instance \mathcal{J} , a perfect matching M , two integers $r, s \in \mathbb{N}$.

Question: Is M a r -robust s -recoverable perfect matching of \mathcal{J} ?

Problem 9 FINDING r -ROBUST s -RECOVERABLE PERFECT MATCHING (FINDING- (r, s) -PM)

Input: A perfect matching instance \mathcal{J} , two integers $r, s \in \mathbb{N}$.

Question: Is there a r -robust s -recoverable perfect matching of \mathcal{J} ?

Remark. Note that similar to [this example](#) of stable matching shown at the beginning of Section 3, we may construct a “zigzag” example of perfect matching where deleting one node will cause a complete re-matching for recovery.

4.1 Hardness Results of FINDING

We focus on the hardness of the FINDING problem of weakly robust recoverable perfect matching, which is the following.

Problem 10 FINDING WEAKLY r -ROBUST s -RECOVERABLE PERFECT MATCHING (FINDING-WEAKLY- (r, s) -PM)

Input: A perfect matching instance \mathcal{J} , two integers $r, s \in \mathbb{N}$.

Question: Is there a weakly r -robust s -recoverable perfect matching of \mathcal{J} ?

We prove that the FINDING-WEAKLY- (r, s) -PM is NP-hard for certain values of the parameters r, s . First we establish the hardness result for the basic case $r = 1$ and $s = 0$, as shown in Theorem 4.1. Then we extend the result to larger r and s in Theorem 4.2 and 4.3.

Remark. As mentioned in the remark at the beginning of this section, 1-robust s -recoverable equivalent to weakly 1-robust s -recoverable for perfect matching. Therefore the hardness results for $r = 1$, which are Theorem 4.1 and 4.3, also apply to FINDING- (r, s) -PM.

Theorem 4.1. FINDING-WEAKLY- $(1, 0)$ -PM is NP-complete.

Proof. This problem is in NP since given a perfect matching, it can always be checked using the LP-based algorithm similar to Theorem 3.1. To show that the problem is NP-hard, we reduce from SET COVER which is the following problem. Note that in the proof we consider the bipartite graph representation of instance of SET COVER as in Figure 11.

Problem 11 SET COVER

Input: A set \mathcal{U} of n elements $\{u_1, \dots, u_n\}$, a family \mathcal{S} of m subsets $\{S_1, \dots, S_m\}$, and an integer k .

Question: Is there a set cover of size $\leq k$?

Figure 11: An instance of SET COVER formulated as a bipartite graph: the left group is the set of elements \mathcal{U} , the right group is the set of subsets \mathcal{S} , node u_i is connected to node S_j if and only if $u_i \in S_j$.

Construction of Theorem 4.1

For any instance of SET COVER where $\mathcal{U} = \{u_1, \dots, u_n\}$, $\mathcal{S} = \{S_1, \dots, S_m\}$ and k is given, we construct a perfect matching instance $G = (A \cup B, E)$ as follows. Let $A = \mathcal{U} \cup A'$ and $B = \mathcal{S} \cup B'$. Here A' is the set of $m - k$ dummy students which connects to all the elements in \mathcal{S} . Denote A as

$$A = \{a_1, \dots, a_n, a'_1, \dots, a'_{m-k}\}, \quad \text{where } a_i = u_i, \forall i = 1, \dots, n.$$

Here B' is the set of n dummy “private” projects b'_i where each connects to exactly one element u_i . Denote B as

$$B = \{b_1, \dots, b_m, b'_1, \dots, b'_n\}, \quad \text{where } b_j = S_j, \forall j = 1, \dots, m.$$

The edges between $\mathcal{U} \subseteq A$ and $\mathcal{S} \subseteq B$ are inherited from the SET COVER instance: a_i is connected to b_j if and only if u_i is an element of S_j , for any i, j . The construction is shown in Figure 12.

Figure 12: Construction of an instance of FINDING-WEAKLY-(1, 0)-PM: the black nodes and edges are inherited from the SET COVER instance, and the blue nodes and edges are the dummy nodes and edges, constructed as above.

We prove that the set cover instance has a set cover of size k if and only if the matching instance has a 1-robust 0-recoverable perfect matching.

For the “only if” part, let $\mathcal{T} \subseteq \mathcal{S}$ be a set cover of size k . Consider the perfect matching where all the a_i is matched to their corresponding “private” dummy project b'_i , and the $m - k$ dummy students are matched in any fixed way to elements in $\{b_1, \dots, b_m\} \setminus \mathcal{T}$. We claim that this perfect matching is 1-robust 0-recoverable. Indeed, if we delete a dummy project b'_i , then we can rematch a_i to some $b_j = S_j \in \mathcal{T}$ since \mathcal{T} is a set cover hence covers a_i . Also deletion of a project matched to dummy students can be easily recovered with no extra rematches.

For the “if” part, let M be a 1-robust 0-recoverable perfect matching of the instance. We claim that, the k elements subset \mathcal{T} of $\mathcal{S} = \{b_1, \dots, b_m\}$ which is not matched in M to any $m - k$ dummy students, is a set cover. Indeed, suppose that there is an element $a_i = u_i \in \mathcal{U}$ is not covered by any subsets in \mathcal{T} , then a_i must be matched to a dummy project b'_j in M . If we delete this dummy project b'_j , then there is no way to recover the matching M using no extra rematches, which is a contradiction. \square

Using the similar idea, we extend the result of Theorem 4.1 to the following two theorems.

Theorem 4.2. FINDING-WEAKLY- $(r, 0)$ -PM is NP-hard, for $1 \leq r \leq \log(n)$.

Proof. To show that the problem is NP-hard, we reduce from SET COVER. For any instance \mathcal{F} of SET COVER, we construct an instance \mathcal{F} of FINDING-WEAKLY- $(r, 0)$ -PM based on the construction used in Theorem 4.1, by adding $r - 1$ copies of the $m - k$ dummy students and $r - 1$ copies of the m projects where every students connects to them in the same way as in the SET COVER instance, to the construction shown in Figure 12. Define

$$A = A_0 \cup A'_1 \cup \dots \cup A'_r \quad \text{and} \quad B = B_1 \cup \dots \cup B_r \cup B',$$

where

- A_0 is a copy of \mathcal{U} ,
- For each $i = 1, \dots, r$, A'_i is the same set of $m - k$ dummy students, and B_i is the same copy of \mathcal{S} corresponds to A'_i . Elements in A'_i and B_i are completely connected, i.e., they form a complete subgraph,
- B' is the set of n dummy “private” projects, whose elements are connected 1-1 with elements of A_0 .

The construction for $r = 2$ is shown in Figure 13. Then we show the following two implications.

Figure 13: Construction of an instance of FINDING-WEAKLY- $(r, 0)$ -PM for $r = 2$: on top of the construction shown in Figure 12, we add 1 copy of $m - k$ dummy students and 1 copy of m projects, colored in teal.

1. If \mathcal{F} has a set cover of size k , then \mathcal{F} has a weakly r -robust 0-recoverable perfect matching.

2. If \mathcal{F} does not have a set cover of size rk , then \mathcal{F} does not have a weakly r -robust 0-recoverable perfect matching.

To show the first implication, let $\mathcal{T} \subseteq \mathcal{S}$ be a set cover of size k , of the instance \mathcal{F} . For each i , let $\mathcal{T}_i \subseteq B_i$ be the corresponding set cover of size k . Consider the matching where elements of A_0 are matched to their corresponding element in B' , and for each i , elements of A'_i are matched in any fixed way to elements in $B_i \setminus \mathcal{T}_i$. We claim that this perfect matching is weakly r -robust 0-recoverable. Indeed, for any deletion R which contains s partners of the dummies and $r - s$ partners of elements in A_0 , it can be recovered by rematching the elements in A_0 to the $r - s$ set covers. The dummies can be recovered with no extra rematches.

To show the second implication, we prove its contrapositive statement. Let M be a weakly r -robust 0-recoverable perfect matching of instance \mathcal{F} . Take the rk elements from all B_i , $1 \leq i \leq r$, which are not matched in M . We claim that it is a set cover of instance \mathcal{F} . Suppose not, say that vertex $a_i = u_i \in A_0$ is not covered by the rk elements, then a_i must be matched to its corresponding private project $b'_i \in B'$ in M . If we delete this b'_i together with any $r - 1$ elements which are matched in M , then there is no way to recover the matching M using no extra rematches, a contradiction.

Since it is NP-hard to distinguish

- YES: \mathcal{F} has a set cover of size k
- NO: \mathcal{F} does not have a set cover of size rk ,

which is proved for example in [17], then it is also NP-hard to distinguish

- YES: \mathcal{F} has a weakly r -robust 0-recoverable perfect matching,
- NO: \mathcal{F} does not have a weakly r -robust 0-recoverable perfect matching.

□

Theorem 4.3. FINDING-WEAKLY-(1, s)-PM is NP-complete, for $1 \leq s \leq n$.

Proof. This problem is in NP since its truthiness can be checked by applying a similar method as in Theorem 3.1. To show that the problem is NP-hard, we reduce from SET COVER. For any instance \mathcal{F} of SET COVER, we construct an instance \mathcal{F} of FINDING-WEAKLY-(1, s)-PM based on the construction used in Theorem 4.1, by adding s many sets of n dummy students and sets of n corresponding private projects to the construction shown in Figure 12. More specifically, we define

$$A = A_0 \cup A_1 \cup \dots \cup A_s \cup A' \quad \text{and} \quad B = B_0 \cup B'_0 \cup \dots \cup B'_s,$$

where

- A_0 is a copy of \mathcal{U} , B_0 is a copy of \mathcal{S} , B'_0 is the set of private projects which connects 1-to-1 with elements of A_0 , A' is the set of $m - k$ dummy students which connects to all elements in B_0 . This part of construction is exactly the same as the construction of Theorem 4.1.
- For each $i = 1, \dots, s$, A_i is a same copy of \mathcal{U} , and B'_i is the set of private projects which connects 1-to-1 with elements of A_i . Moreover, A_i connects 1-to-1 with elements of B'_{i-1} .

Figure 14: Construction of an instance of FINDING-WEAKLY-(1, s)-PM for $s = 1$, on top of the construction shown in Figure 12, we add 1 copy of n dummy students and 1 copy of their private projects, colored in cyan.

Figure 14 shows the case when $s = 1$.

We prove that the set cover instance has a set cover of size k if and only if the matching instance has a weakly 1-robust 0-recoverable perfect matching.

First if \mathcal{F} has a set cover of size k , say \mathcal{T} , then consider the perfect matching M where elements of A_i are matched to their corresponding private project in B'_i , for $0 \leq i \leq s$, and elements of A' are matched in any fixed way to elements in $B_0 \setminus \mathcal{T}$. Then M is weakly 1-robust s -recoverable, since for $0 \leq i \leq s$ deleting any single node of B'_i requires i extra rematches and deleting any single node of $M(A')$ requires 0 extra rematches.

Next if \mathcal{F} has a weakly 1-robust s -recoverable perfect matching M , then take the k elements \mathcal{T} in $\mathcal{S} = B_0$ which are not matched in M to any elements of A' . This is a set cover of $\mathcal{U} = A_0$. Suppose not, say $a \in \mathcal{U} = A_0$ is not covered by \mathcal{T} , then for each $0 \leq i \leq s$, the corresponding copy of a in A_i must be matched to its private project b'_i . If we delete b'_i , then it requires more than s extra rematches to recover, a contradiction. \square

Remark. Table 2 summarizes the hardness results we have proved in Theorem 4.1, 4.2, and 4.3 for the FINDING problem of perfect matching.

$r \backslash s$	0	1	...	n
1	NP-complete	NP-complete	...	NP-complete
2	NP-complete	?	...	?
\vdots	\vdots	\vdots	\ddots	\vdots
$\log(n)$	NP-hard	?	...	?

Table 2: Complexity of FINDING-WEAKLY- (r, s) -PM for different values of r, s

4.2 Integrality Gap

Similar to the case for stable matching, the optimization version of FINDING problem for perfect matching, i.e., the problem FINDING- (r, s) -PM, can be formulated as

$$\begin{aligned}
\min \quad & d \\
\text{s.t.} \quad & x \in P_M, x \in \{0, 1\}^E, \\
& y_R \in P_M(R), y_R \in \{0, 1\}^E, \forall R \subseteq B, |R| = r, \\
& d \geq \|x - y_R\|_1, \forall R \subseteq B, |R| = r,
\end{aligned} \tag{10}$$

where $P_M(R)$ is the matching polytope after deletion of R . Here d represents the total number of rematches, whereas the parameter s represents the extra number of rematches. Therefore, the solution of (10) is $\leq r + s$ if and only if the answer to FINDING- (r, s) -PM is yes.

Remark. Unlikely stable matching, we do have

$$P_M(R) = P_M \cap \{x \in \mathbb{R}^E : x_e = 0, \forall e \in \delta(v), \forall v \in R\},$$

hence for each R , the polytope $P_M(R)$ is contained in P_M .

Essentially the FINDING problem is that, we want to find a perfect matching x such that the ℓ_1 -ball around x intersects the set of vertices of $P_M(R)$ for all possible deletion subsets $R \subseteq B$ of size r , which is illustrated in Figure 15.

An interesting question is to give an approximation of the total number of rematches $r + s$, which is equivalently d as in the formulation (10). The next example gives a lower bound of the approximation factor.

Example. Consider the following special perfect matching instance with $r = 1$, where elements of A are d -regular with $d \geq 2$ and elements of B are 2-regular. Figure 16 illustrates this instance when $d = 5$. A feasible fractional solution of (10) is given as follows. Take

$$x_e = \frac{1}{d} \cdot \mathbf{1}^E,$$

Figure 15: Illustration of formulation (10)

and for each $R \subseteq B$, $|R| = 1$, let $v_R \in B$ be the deletion node, then we take

$$(y_R)_e = \begin{cases} 0, & \text{if } v_R \in e, \\ \frac{1}{d-1}, & \text{if there exists } u \in A \text{ adjacent to } v_R \text{ such that } u \in e, \\ \frac{1}{d}, & \text{otherwise,} \end{cases}$$

which implies that

$$s \geq 2 \left(\left(\frac{1}{d} - 0 \right) + (d-1) \left(\frac{1}{d-1} - \frac{1}{d} \right) \right) = \frac{4}{d} \Rightarrow \text{OPT}_f \leq \frac{4}{d}.$$

Obviously $\text{OPT} \geq 1$. Therefore we get a lower bound of the integrality gap of our formulation

$$\frac{\text{OPT}}{\text{OPT}_f} \geq \frac{d}{4}.$$

Figure 16: Instance of perfect matching problem with regular bipartite graph

Remark. This example shows that this LP relaxation is somewhat weak for getting a good approximation. One may consider using LP hierarchies to get a stronger relaxation, for example the Sherali-Adams hierarchy.

4.3 Conjecture for CHECKING

We have shown in Section 3.1 that the CHECKING- (r, s) -SM problem can be solved in polynomial time for any constant r . This LP-based algorithm method also applies to CHECKING- (r, s) -PM problem since the perfect matching polytope is also integral. However we wonder if for CHECKING- (r, s) -PM problem, there exists a better LP-based algorithm than the one for CHECKING- (r, s) -SM problem. One of our attempts is to reduce the CHECKING- (r, s) -PM problem where r is of strict higher order than constant⁹, to the CHECKING- (r, s) -PM problem when $r = 1$.

For any subset $R \subseteq B$, define $f(R)$ as the optimal solution of the following linear program

$$\begin{aligned} \max \quad & \sum_{e \in M} x_e \\ \text{s.t.} \quad & x \in P_M(R), \\ & x \in \{0, 1\}^E. \end{aligned} \tag{11}$$

In particular, for any b_i where $i = 1, \dots, m$, define $f(b_i) := f(\{b_i\})$. Then reorder b_i in ascending order based on $f(b_i)$, i.e., $f(b_1) \leq f(b_2) \leq \dots \leq f(b_m)$. The smaller $f(b_i)$ is, the more “vulnerable” deletion of b_i is, since deletion of b_i needs more rematches for recovery. Consider the CHECKING- (r, s) -PM problem for a given perfect bipartite matching M .

Conjecture 2. For any $r \in \{1, \dots, m\}$, M is r -robust s -recoverable if and only if

$$n - (r + s) \leq f(\{b_1, \dots, b_r\}).$$

Intuitively this conjecture suggests that the problem CHECKING- (r, s) -PM is reduced to CHECKING- (R, s) -PM where $R = \{b_1, \dots, b_r\}$, which is set of the most vulnerable r nodes of deletion.

If this conjecture is true, then we instantly get a polynomial-time algorithm for CHECKING- (r, s) -PM problem for any r , since CHECKING- (R, s) -PM is polynomial-time solvable for any R .

Remark. Although this conjecture being true would give us a positive result for the CHECKING- (r, s) -PM problem, we guess it is the opposite. The reason is that deletion of nodes seems to be not independent to each other. However we haven’t found a counterexample yet.

⁹For example $O(\log(n))$, $O(n)$ etc.

5 Relation between Rotation and Pivoting

We turn our attention to the structural question of stable matchings. As shown in Section 2, the set of stable matchings have both the lattice structure and the polytope structure. For each structure, there is a way to transform one stable matching into another:

- Rotation can help us traverse the stable matching lattice,
- Pivoting can help us traverse the stable matching polytope.

A natural question is then to ask the relationship between these two transformations. This question is settled in this section: we prove that rotation is a special pivoting but not the other way around. We also find that for some matching instances, the set of edges of stable matching polytope is not necessarily included in the set of edges of the matching polytope.

Throughout this section, the stable matching instance is assumed to be a complete balanced bipartite graph with $2n$ vertices, i.e., $|A| = |B| = n$.

We use the word adjacency interchangeably with pivoting. They are essentially the same since two stable matchings differ by pivoting is equivalent to say that they are adjacent in the stable matching polytope.

Rotation implies pivoting

Theorem 5.1. If there are two stable matchings where one can be transformed into another by a rotation ρ , denoted as M and M/ρ , then M and M/ρ are adjacent in the stable matching polytope P_{SM} .

Proof. For general polytope, we have the following results.

Lemma 5.2. Let P be a polytope and $Ax \leq b$ be a system of linear inequalities. Let $Q = P \cap \{Ax \leq b\}$. Suppose that the set of vertices of Q is a subset of the set of vertices of P . For any two vertices u, v of Q , if they are adjacent in P , then they are also adjacent in Q .

Now we apply Lemma 5.2 to our problem. Let P be the matching polytope P_M and Q be the stable matching polytope P_{SM} . Here the linear inequalities $Ax \leq b$ are simply the stability constraint, as shown in (4). Since the set of vertices of P_{SM} is a subset of the set of vertices of P_M , we can apply this lemma to any rotation ρ and two stable matchings M and M/ρ , to deduce that M and M/ρ are adjacent in P_{SM} . \square

Pivoting does not imply rotation

Now we focus on the other direction. Recall that the adjacency of perfect matching polytope is characterized by the following theorem.

Theorem 5.3 ([20], Theorem 18.4). Let M and N be two perfect matchings of an undirected graph $G = (V, E)$. Then χ^M and χ^N are adjacent vertices of the perfect matching polytope if and only if $M \Delta N$ is a circuit.

The difficulty of this direction is that there is no such similar characterization of adjacency for stable matching polytope. We can decompose the set of edges¹⁰ of P_{SM} , which is denoted as $E_{SM} := E(P_{SM})$, as follows

$$E_{SM} = (E_{SM} \cap E_M) \cup (E_{SM} \setminus E_M).$$

Therefore there are two possible ways to find an example, i.e., two adjacent stable matchings which do not differ by rotation.

1. Find an example from $E_{SM} \setminus E_M$. In fact, it suffices to find **any element** from $E_{SM} \setminus E_M$, that is, to show that $E_{SM} \setminus E_M$ is nonempty. This is because of the following lemma.

Lemma 5.4. Let M and N be two stable matchings which are adjacent in P_{SM} but not in P_M , i.e., MN is in $E_{SM} \setminus E_M$. Then M and N do not differ by rotations.

Proof. By Theorem 5.3, two stable matchings differ by rotation implies that they are adjacent in P_M . \square

Remark. Although it's commonly believed that $E_{SM} \not\subseteq E_M$, to the best of our knowledge, so far this question has not been settled by anyone.

2. Find an example from $E_{SM} \cap E_M$.

We manage to find examples from both categories as follows.

Example (“Pivoting but not rotation”). Consider the matching instance of 4 students denoted as 1, 2, 3, 4 and 4 projects denoted as A, B, C, D , which is taken from [4]. The preference lists are given as follows. There are 10 stable matchings of this instance, which form a lattice as shown in Figure 18. The

1	A	B	C	D	A	4	3	2	1
2	B	A	D	C	B	3	4	1	2
3	C	D	A	B	C	2	1	4	3
4	D	C	B	A	D	1	2	3	4

Figure 17: Preference lists of students (left) and projects (right)

stable matching is denoted as a permutation, for example, $[1\ 2\ 3\ 4]$ represents the stable matching $\{1A, 2B, 3C, 4D\}$. We compute the adjacency using SageMath. Out of all $\binom{10}{2} = 45$ pairs of stable matchings, only 6 of them are not adjacent to each other, which are

$$[1\ 2\ 3\ 4] \text{ and } [2\ 1\ 4\ 3], \quad [2\ 1\ 4\ 3] \text{ and } [3\ 4\ 1\ 2], \quad [3\ 4\ 1\ 2] \text{ and } [4\ 3\ 2\ 1], \\ [2\ 1\ 3\ 4] \text{ and } [1\ 2\ 4\ 3], \quad [3\ 1\ 4\ 2] \text{ and } [2\ 4\ 1\ 3], \quad [4\ 3\ 1\ 2] \text{ and } [3\ 4\ 2\ 1].$$

In Figure 19 we highlight in orange these non-adjacent pairs. From the rest 39 adjacent pairs, we find the following two examples, where the adjacent stable matchings do not differ by rotations, from **both types of adjacency**.

¹⁰In this part we will use the notion of edge to

Figure 18: The stable matching lattice

Proposition 5.5. For this matching instance, there are two stable matchings shown in Figure 20a:

$$M = [1\ 2\ 3\ 4] = \{1A, 2B, 3C, 4D\}, \quad N_1 = [3\ 4\ 1\ 2] = \{1C, 2D, 3A, 4B\},$$

such that M and N_1 are adjacent in P_{SM} but not in P_M , hence M and N_2 do not differ by rotation.

Proof. First we show that M, N_1 are adjacent in P_{SM} . Consider the following 15 linearly independent inequalities which includes

- 8 non-negativity constraints of type (1) for

$$1B, 1D, 2A, 2C, 3B, 3D, 4A, 4C,$$

- 7 stability constraints of type (4) for

$$1A, 1B, 1D, 2A, 2C, 3A, 4A.$$

Both M and N_1 are active at these 15 inequalities. Moreover M is active at the non-negativity constraint for $2D$ and N_1 is active at the non-negativity constraint for $2B$. Each of them, together with the 15 inequalities, form an independent set of inequalities for M and N_1 respectively.

Next we compute that

$$M \Delta N_1 = \{1 - A - 3 - C - 1\} \cup \{2 - B - 4 - D - 2\}$$

which is not a circuit. By Theorem 5.3, M, N_1 are not adjacent in P_M , □

Remark. By Proposition 5.5, this matching instance gives an example of $E_{SM} \not\subseteq E_M$.

Figure 19: The non-adjacent pairs, each colored in orange

Proposition 5.6. For this matching instance, there are two stable matchings shown in Figure 20b:

$$M = [1 \ 2 \ 3 \ 4] = \{1A, 2B, 3C, 4D\}, \quad N_2 = [3 \ 1 \ 4 \ 2] = \{1C, 2A, 3D, 4B\},$$

such that M and N_2 are adjacent in both P_{SM} and in P_M , but not differ by rotation.

Proof. First note that

$$M \Delta N_2 = \{1 - A - 2 - B - 4 - D - 3 - C - 1\}$$

is a circuit, which by Theorem 5.3 implies that M, N_2 are adjacent in P_M . By Lemma 5.2, M, N_2 are also adjacent in P_{SM} . Next we prove that M and N_2 do not differ by any rotation. In our case,

$$\rho = ((1, A), (3, C), (4, D), (2, B)).$$

However according to Definition 2.10, for the stable matching M , C is not the successor of 1 (which is B), and B is not the successor of 4 (which is C). \square

Figure 20: Two examples of “pivoting but not rotation”

6 Open Questions

- For the robust recoverable problem of stable matching, one may try to establish some parameterized hardness results of the FINDING problem, for example $W[1]$ -hardness with respect to r .

Another interesting direction for further research is to find a polynomial-time algorithm for CHECKING when r is of higher order than constant or prove that this problem is hard.

- For the robust recoverable problem of perfect matching, one possible direction is to complete Table 2 by establishing hardness results for other values of r, s .

Moreover, inspired by the computation of a lower bound of the integrality gap in Section 4.2, one may consider the case where every students choose d projects, i.e., the graph is d -regular on one side.¹¹ It would be interesting to find an approximation algorithm of $r + s$, which is the total number of rematches, hopefully with a factor of approximation being $O(d)$. One could also look for inapproximability results for the general case.

- For the structural of stable matchings, an interesting question is to give a characterization of adjacency for the stable matching polytope, potentially as certain composition of rotations.

¹¹This is actually similar to the setting of our real-world matching problem: students are supposed to choose between 3 to 5 projects, which is close to be “regular”.

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